
Research Article

New combinations in Amaryllidaceae

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Abstract: Molecular evidence supports the inclusion of *Habranthus* Herb. within *Zephyranthes* Herb. Consequently, four species formerly placed in *Habranthus* are here transferred to *Zephyranthes*. In addition, morphological characters described in the protologue of *Amaryllis nervosa* Poir. (\equiv *Amaryllis striata* Jacq.) support its placement in *Brunsvigia* Heist., for which a new combination is provided. A lectotype is also designated for *Habranthus flavus* Phil.

Keywords: *Amaryllis*, *Brunsvigia*, Chile, *Habranthus*, Lectotype, South Africa, *Zephyranthes*

Introduction

Recent molecular phylogenetic studies have shown that *Habranthus* Herb. is congeneric with *Zephyranthes* Herb. (García et al., 2019). Accordingly, four species previously assigned to *Habranthus* are here transferred to *Zephyranthes*. A lectotype is designated here for the name *Habranthus flavus* Phil. in accordance with Art. 9 of the International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi, and plants (Turland et al., 2025). Furthermore, the vegetative and floral characters described in the protologue of *Amaryllis nervosa* Poir. (\equiv *Amaryllis striata* Jacq.) are consistent with those of *Brunsvigia* Heist., supporting its transfer to that genus.

New combinations

Brunsvigia nervosa (Poir.) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

\equiv *Amaryllis nervosa* Poir., Encycl., Suppl. 1: 321. 1810. *Amaryllis striata* Jacq., Pl. Rar. Hort. Schoenbr. 1: 36. 1797, *nom. illeg., non* Lam., Encycl. [J. Lamarck & al.] 1: 125. 1783. *Brunsvigia striata* (Jacq.) W.T.Aiton, Hort. Kew., ed. 2 [W.T. Aiton] 2: 231. 1811, *nom. illeg. et superfl.*

Holotype: South Africa, Cape of Good Hope, *s.d.*, *F. Masson s.n.* (BM000911875!, Figure 1).

Distribution: South Africa (Cape Provinces).

Zephyranthes bakeri (Phil.) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Habranthus bakeri* Phil., *Anales Univ. Chile* 93: 150. 1896. *Amaryllis bakeri* (Phil.) Traub & Uphof, *Herbertia* 5: 130. 1938. *Rhodophiala bakeri* (Phil.) Traub, *Pl. Life (Stanford)* 9: 60. 1953.

Type: Chile, Talca Province, Maule, *Fridericus filius s.n.* (SGO).

Distribution: Chile (Talca Province, Maule Region).

Notes: Herbarium specimen of this species collected in 1969 is traced at L (L1454657!, Figure 2).

Zephyranthes consobrina (Phil.) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Hippeastrum consobrinum* Phil., *Anales Univ. Chile* 93: 152. 1896. *Amaryllis consobrina* (Phil.) Traub & Uphof, *Herbertia* 5: 131. 1938, *nom. illeg., non* Sweet ex Gorrie, *Miller's Dict. Gard.* 186. 1834. *Rhodophiala consobrina* (Phil.) Traub, *Pl. Life (Stanford)* 9: 59. 1953.

Type: Chile, Santiago, *Anon. s.n.* (SGO).

Distribution: Chile (Santiago Province).

Zephyranthes lineata (Phil.) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Habranthus lineatus* Phil., *Anales Univ. Chile* 43: 542. 1873. *Hippeastrum lineatum* (Phil.) Baker, *J. Bot.* 16: 82. 1878. *Amaryllis lineata* (Phil.) Traub & Uphof, *Herbertia* 5: 122. 1938, *nom. illeg., non* Lam., *Encycl. [J. Lamarck & al.]* 1(1): 123. 1783. *Rhodophiala lineata* (Phil.) Traub, *Pl. Life (Stanford)* 9: 60. 1953.

Holotype: Chile, Andibus, Santiago, 20 December 1871, *R.A. Philippi s.n.* (SGO000001046!).

Distribution: Chile (Santiago Province).

Zephyranthes solisii (Phil.) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Hippeastrum solisii* Phil., *Anales Univ. Chile* 93: 155. 1896. *Amaryllis solisii* (Phil.) Traub & Uphof, *Herbertia* 5: 131. 1938. *Habranthus flavus* Phil., *Anales Univ. Chile* 27: 333. 1865. *Amaryllis flava* (Phil.) Traub & Uphof, *Herbertia* 6: 150. 1940. *Rhodophiala flava* (Phil.) Traub, *Pl. Life (Stanford)* 9: 60. 1953. *Hippeastrum flavum* (Phil.) Christenh. & Byng, *Global Fl.* 4: 60. 2018.

Lectotype (designated here): Chile, Chillán, Hacienda de Colicheo, 1864, *M.A. de Solis s.n.* (SGO000001045!); isolectotypes F0BN009973!, SGO000001044!.

Distribution: Chile (Ñuble Region).

Figure 1: Holotype of *Amaryllis striata* Jacq. (BM000911875, © The Natural History Museum, London)

Figure 2: *Habranthus bakeri* Phil. (L1454657, © Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden)

Notes: Three specimens were traced for the name *Habranthus flavus* Phil. (FOBN009973, SGO000001044 and SGO000001045). Among these, the better-preserved specimen SGO000001045, is designated here as the lectotype as it agrees well with the protologue.

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